

Studies on Complexes of Isoquinoline with Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II) Alkanoates

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A number of metal complexes of the type $M(O_2CR)_2(IQ)_2$ (where $M=Co(II)$; $R=H-, CH_3-, C_2H_5-, n-$ and $iso-C_3H_7-$ and C_4H_9- and $M=Ni(II)$; $R=CH_3-$ and C_2H_5- and $IQ=Isoquinoline$) have been isolated by treating the appropriate metal(II) alkanoate with a large excess of isoquinoline in chloroform and are characterized by magnetic and spectral studies which show that the complexes possess a trans octahedral structure containing bidentate chelating carboxylate groups.

Cobalt(II) and nickel(II) acetates are known to form a number of addition complexes¹⁻⁵ with heterocyclic ligands like pyridines, quinoline, morpholine, piperidine, piperazine and N-methylpyrazine which have been shown to be 6-coordinated octahedral monomeric complexes excepting quinoline adduct of nickel(II) acetate which has a polymeric structure. Some complexes of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) alkanoates derived from propionic, n- and iso-butyric and n-valeric acids with pyridine have also been prepared⁶. Since no structural studies have been done on these complexes, it was considered interesting to prepare some more complexes of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) alkanoates with a related ligand like isoquinoline and to investigate their structure by magnetic and spectroscopic methods.

Experimental

Cobalt(II) and nickel(II) alkanoates were prepared by published methods⁶. Isoquinoline was fractionally distilled over KOH pellets. Solvents were purified by conventional methods.

Preparation of Complexes: Complexes were prepared by treating a suspension of the appropriate

metal(II) alkanoate in chloroform with a large excess of the ligand under reflux for half an hour. The resulting clear solution was filtered and excess of the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The remaining viscous liquid on keeping for 24 hr over concentrated sulphuric acid in a vacuum desiccator gave a coloured crystalline compound which was recrystallized from methanol and dried over phosphorus pentoxide in vacuum at room temperature.

Cobalt in these complexes was estimated as tetrapyridinedithiocyanato-cobalt(II) and nickel as bis(dimethylglyoximato)-nickel(II). Carbon and hydrogen analyses were carried out in the micro-analytical laboratory of this department.

Magnetic moments were determined by Gouy's method using $Hg[Co(NCS)_4]$ as calibrant. Electronic spectra were recorded in benzene on Beckmann DU-2 Spectrophotometer over the range 360-1250 nm. Infrared spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer models 337 and 621. The analytical, molecular weight and magnetic data of the complexes prepared are presented in Table 1 while infrared and electronic spectra are cited in Table 2.

TABLE-1: ANALYTICAL, MOLECULAR AND MAGNETIC DATA OF COMPLEXES OF ISOQUINOLINE WITH COBALT(II) AND NICKEL(II) ALKANOATES

Sl. No	Compound	Colour	Metal (%)		Carbon (%)		Hydrogen (%)		M. Wt		μ_{eff} B.M.
			Found	Calcd	Found	Calcd	Found	Calcd	Found	Calcd	
1.	Co(formate) ₂ (IQ) ₂	Pink	14.29	14.47	58.58	58.92	3.67	3.92	—	407	4.87
2.	Co(acetate) ₂ (IQ) ₂	Pink	13.27	13.54	60.38	60.63	4.48	4.59	413	435	4.89
3.	Co(propionate) ₂ (IQ) ₂	Red	12.56	12.72	61.86	62.15	5.02	5.17	452	463	4.93
4.	Co(n-butyrate) ₂ (IQ) ₂	Red	11.78	11.99	63.41	63.49	5.32	5.69	502	491	4.94
5.	Co(iso-butyrate) ₂ (IQ) ₂	Red	11.71	11.99	63.62	63.49	5.38	5.69	480	491	4.89
6.	Co(n-valerate) ₂ (IQ) ₂	Red	11.04	11.34	64.71	64.69	5.94	6.15	—	519	4.94
7.	Co(iso-valerate) ₂ (IQ) ₂	Red	11.13	11.34	64.65	64.69	5.87	6.15	—	519	4.98
8.	Ni(acetate) ₂ (IQ) ₂	Light blue	13.14	13.49	59.95	60.87	5.38	5.59	402	435	3.18
9.	Ni(propionate) ₂ (IQ) ₂	Light blue	12.61	12.68	62.03	62.19	4.93	5.18	421	463	3.20

TABLE-2: IMPORTANT INFRARED ABSORPTION FREQUENCIES (cm⁻¹) AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRA (nm) (ε) OF COMPLEXES OF ISOQUINOLINE WITH COBALT(II) AND NICKEL(II) ALKANOATES

Compound*	ν(C=C and C=N)					ν(COO)		Δ	ν(O-M)	ν(N-M)	λ _{max} (ε)
						Asym.	Sym.				
Isoquinoline	1630	1590	1500	1465	1440	-	-	-	-	-	-
	1640 sh	1595	1510	1470	-	1615	1420	195	265	218	-
1.									283		
2.	-	1610	1510	1468	-	1625	1418	207	270	225	492 sh, 527(43), 1175(7)
3.	-	1595	1500	1465	1445	1630	1421	209	273	212	490 sh, 505(45), 1156(6)
4.	1640 sh	1600	1520	1473	1445	1635	1431	204	288	215	487 sh, 502(38), 1160(6)
									292		
5.	-	1610	1515	1470	1445	1628	1410	218	285	215	483 sh, 520(35), 1181(7)
6.	1640 sh	1608	1520	1468	-	1625	1421	204	260	218	486 sh, 515(47), 1156(8)
									285		
7.	1635 sh	1609	1509	1475	-	1627	1416	211	275	218	490 sh, 510(30), 1160(6)
8.	1638 sh	1610	1520	1463	-	1631	1420	211	282	210	385(15), 630(9), 1035(3)
9.	-	1610	1505	1465	-	1633	1420	213	280	212	375(11), 642(7), 1038(4)

*Number refers to compounds in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data (Table 1) indicate that complexes are of 1:2 stoichiometry of formula M(O₂CR)₂(IQ)₂. The complexes are generally soluble in common organic solvents and are quite stable in air. However, iso-quinoline complex of cobalt(II) formate is insoluble in nature. Cobalt complexes are pink or red in colour while nickel complexes are light blue in colour. Molar conductance of 10⁻³M solutions of these complexes in nitrobenzene is below 2 ohm⁻¹cm²mole⁻¹ which suggest that complexes are non-electrolytes⁷. Molecular weights indicate that the complexes are monomeric in solution. Magnetic moment values for cobalt complexes fall in the range 4.87-4.98 B.M. and for nickel complexes in the range 3.18-3.20 B.M. which point that the complexes are high spin and have octahedral stereochemistry. The electronic spectra of cobalt complexes show two main absorption bands around 1175 and 500 nm as expected for octahedral symmetry and may be assigned to ⁴T_{1g}→⁴T_{2g} and ⁴T_{1g}→⁴T_{1g}(P) transitions respectively. The nickel complexes exhibited the usual three main bands characteristic of octahedral complexes around 1035, 630 and 385 nm and are assigned to ³A_{2g}→³T_{2g}, ³A_{2g}→³T_{1g} and ³A_{2g}→³T_{1g}(P) electronic transitions. Low values of molar extinction coefficients (ε Ca. 47 l. mole⁻¹cm⁻¹) suggest that the complexes are of ^ttrans octahedral configuration⁸.

Infrared spectra of the complexes show similar features indicating that all the complexes are isostructural. The bands due to C=C and C=N stretching frequencies of the isoquinoline ligand are shifted to higher frequencies indicating the coordination of the ligand through its nitrogen atom in agreement with the observations made by previous workers⁹. The asymmetric (COO) stretching frequencies fall in the range 1635-1615 cm⁻¹ while symmetric (COO) stretching frequencies occur in the range 1431-1410 cm⁻¹. The difference between asymme-

tric and symmetric (COO) stretching frequencies, Δ, in the complexes works out to be around 200 cm⁻¹ which falls in the same range as observed for some pyridine¹⁰ complexes of cobalt(II) acetate and propionate which contain bidentate chelating carboxylate group. This suggests that mode of bonding of the alkanooate group in the present complexes is also bidentate chelating. The bands observed in the region 292-260 and 225-210 cm⁻¹ have been tentatively assigned to ν_{M-O} and ν_{M-N} vibrations analogous to ν_{M-O} and ν_{M-N} stretching vibrations of amine-metal(II) trifluoroacetate¹¹ which fall in the region 325-235 and 228-195 cm⁻¹ respectively.

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